

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D4.3 Social media monitoring tool

WP4 – Engagement and motivation strategies for youth
participation

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the development and deployment of the initial version of the STEP social media monitoring tool. It describes the usage scenario and functionality together with implementation details. The prototype application targeting environmental policy makers is presented here, whilst a reduced version targeting citizens is presented in terms of the integrated STEP platform in D3.2 Integrated and tested STEP platform. Modifications are continued on the applications throughout the whole lifetime of the project including the improvement of research modules.

The web tool for STEP social media mining is released at:
http://188.214.128.140/ui/index.html?user_id=1234567890.

This deliverable initially presents a description of the functional and non-functional user requirements, targeting the different types of user: (a) policy makers and authorities that are interested in planning their environmental campaigns, monitor interesting environmental issues, and analyse results using the component's dashboard, feed and visualisations, and b) young citizens that are interested in specific environmental issues and wish to discover relevant discussions in social media.

The features of the STEP social media monitoring tool include:

- Creating collections from social media platforms (Twitter, Facebook, Google+, YouTube, Flickr) and RSS feeds by entering keywords and/or user accounts of interest;
- Collection of content in the form of items (posts made in social platforms, e.g. tweets, Facebook and YouTube videos, etc.);
- Collection of contributors of social media content;
- Detection of dominant topics and languages in each collection;
- Filtering of items in a collection based on language, platform (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, etc.), publication date (since-until) and originality (original content or shared);
- Sorting of items according to publication time (recency), popularity and relevance;
- Analytics over collections with a number of visualisation widgets.

Next we present implementation details for the tool, as well as the developed API, which is the backbone of the prototype, enabling integration of the tool with the core STEP platform.

Finally we provide a section with an example case study as well as a discussion about the limitations of the current tool and the associated plan for future developments.

2 Introduction

The STEP social media monitoring tool was designed with the aim: a) to allow public servants to monitor in social media the impact of their environmental campaigns, as well as any other topics of interest; and b) to enable citizens who engage within the STEP e-participation platform to browse social media content relevant to their own topics of interest, with the goal of getting up-to-date on important matters and driving more vivid discussions on the e-participation part of the STEP platform, and ultimately providing more insights about the issues discussed and more content shared.

Two main views of the tool have been designed for use in the STEP platform:

- a) Authorities view: This is the full version of the tool allowing the authorities to plan their environmental campaigns, monitor interesting environmental issues, and analyse results using the component's dashboard, feed and visualisations.
- b) Citizens view: This is a reduced version of the tool which is integrated in the STEP platform allowing citizens to declare their topics of interest and receive relevant content items from social media that can be consequently used as regular content items in the context of the e-participation component.

To this end, the initial version of the STEP social media monitoring tool was deployed for the two above use cases. The development methodology involved the following steps:

- a) At first stage, focus group discussions were held with end users and pilots, where all four pilots, as well as DRAXIS and YEE were involved in order to provide feedback on how to populate and adapt the existing social media monitoring tool¹ to the environmental context of the project. As a result, we collected for each pilot case, as well as at a pan-European level, collections of relevant topics, keywords, social media pages and accounts, that were in turn used to create initial content collections tailored around each pilot area and around dominant environmental topics at the European level.
- b) This initial requirements analysis phase showed that pilot users were not familiar at the beginning of the project with the capabilities of social media monitoring tools (even at a conceptual level), and therefore these users were not able at that point to capture its full potential. Therefore, it was decided that:
 - i. pilot users should be acquainted with the social media monitoring tool capabilities as soon as possible in order to provide valuable feedback,
 - ii. the initial deployment of the tool should be integrated in the platform at an early stage to offer a core set of services (that CERTH had already at its disposal at the beginning of the project), and
 - iii. the deployment of updated and new features for the tool should be specifically tailored around the actual needs of the platform users, and should be postponed only after the pilot users could grasp well the capabilities of the system and provide concrete feedback.

¹ As will be explained below, at the beginning of the project, CERTH presented an existing version of the tool that had been developed in the context of the FP7 SocialSensor project.

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- c) For the initial setup of the social media monitoring tool we relied on an existing implementation (which had been developed during the FP7 SocialSensor Integrated Project²). The tool performs collection of content from social media platforms in the form of Items (posts made in a social media platform, e.g. tweets, facebook posts, etc.), WebPages (URLs embedded in collected Items) and MediaItems (images and videos embedded in Items or WebPages). Also Users that publish content or are mentioned in it are collected. The social media monitoring tool comprises three modules: a) the Stream manager, b) the Focused social media crawler, and c) the visualisation component. The full version of the social media monitoring tool interface is available to policy makers only, whilst for the citizens use case, only widgets from the Visualisation component are provided to the end users, which contain already crawled content, maps and statistics, filtered according to keywords and topics provided by the user in his/her STEP platform user profile.
- d) After a first version of the tool was available to the consortium for testing, user feedback from the pilot cases was gathered in order to design the updated version of the tool. Users and pilots were made aware of the tool potential and thus they were able to provide useful and concrete feedback through the pilots' workshops and the citizens' co-creation workshops (T3.2.4 Adaptation according to pilot requirements). Based on this feedback, continuous improvement and addition of new and relevant features will drive the development of the updated versions of the tool's.

The remaining sections of this document are structured as follows.

Section 3 provides an overview of the functional and non-functional user requirements that have been gathered from the target groups of authorities and citizens. It then presents the basic functionalities of the tool in Section 4, which also presents several elements of the actual User Interface of the tool. Section 5 provides implementation details for each of the described modules of Section 4, along with the API used for integration of the tool to the STEP platform. Section 6 presents the functionality of the tool under a specific use case scenario. Section 7 discusses limitations and future work, describing also some of the foreseen features for the updated version of the tool, while Annex I presents some examples of widgets that are used in the STEP platform for the support of the citizens' use case.

² <http://socialsensor.eu/>

3 Requirements

As a result from the User requirements gathering phase (see D2.2 Report on users' needs and technical requirements), the STEP social media monitoring tool, being part of the STEP platform, is targeting mainly two distinct groups:

- (a) **Authorities:** These users are interested in planning environmental campaigns, monitoring interesting environmental issues, viewing insights and analysing the collected content. To this end, they are expected to take advantage of the full version of the tool, including all its capabilities.
- (b) **Citizens:** The audience in this case mainly comprises young citizens who use the STEP platform as an e-participation tool and are active contributors. These will also be able to benefit from the social media content gathered from the social media monitoring tool in a personalised manner. Citizens can declare their topics of interest in the main STEP platform and consequently receive relevant content items from social media that can be used as regular content items in the context of the e-participation component. The social media monitoring features are in this case integrated within the e-participation module in the form of widgets. Examples of such widgets are presented in Annex I of this deliverable, as well as in D3.2 Integrated and tested STEP platform.

In the following we present the functional and non-functional requirements gathered for the tool during the User requirements phase.

3.1 Functional Requirements

The Social Media monitoring tool is responsible for the collection of content from social media platforms in the form of **Items** (posts made in a social platform, e.g. tweets, facebook posts, etc.), **WebPages** (URLs embedded in collected Items) and **MediaItems** (images and videos embedded in Items or WebPages). Also **Users** that publish content or are mentioned in it are collected.

The functional requirements (FR) are presented below:

<FR-1> **The user has to be able to insert a new source of interest into the system for monitoring.**

Description: The end user or any other external system that uses the social media component has to be able to insert a new source of interest into the system. Namely, there are four different types of supported sources:

1. **Keyword-based:** this source consists of a set of keywords combined with logical operators (AND, OR, NOT). When the user inserts such a source the system has to collect items from social media that are related to the keywords, with respect to the logical operators.
2. **Account-based:** this source is based on a set of accounts. Namely, the end user can specify a set of accounts they wish to monitor. For each account the user has also to specify the social media platform that the account belongs to (e.g. YouTube for YouTube channels, Facebook for Facebook pages, etc.).

3. **Location-based:** with this source the user can define a location by name e.g. Thessaloniki, or by using a bounding box. The system will collect social media items that are geotagged and the tag is inside the selected location. Note that this type of source is only available for the platforms that support geolocation.
4. **Hybrid source:** any logical combination of the previous three source types.

Priority (5/5): This feature is a core functionality of the system, so it is considered as a task of high priority. However the location-based sources can be considered as an optional feature, as covers only few platforms.

Stability (5/5): This requirement is unlikely to change in future versions of the system.

<FR-2> **The user should be able to delete a source of interest, previously inserted by him/her.**

Description: The user should be able to delete a source that had been inserted by him/her. This action should remove the source from the list of sources monitored by the user.

Priority (5/5): This is a core action of the user regarding the management of sources, so it is considered of high priority.

Stability (5/5): This requirement is unlikely to change in future versions of the system.

<FR-3> **The user should be able to get a list of sources, inserted by him/her.**

Description: The end user has to be able to see the list of sources, inserted by him/her.

Priority (5/5): This is a core action of the user regarding the management of sources, so it is considered of high priority.

Stability (5/5): This requirement is unlikely to change in future versions of the system.

<FR-4> **The user has to be able to retrieve social media items related to a source.**

Description: The user has to be able to get a list of relevant social media items. Items with low relevance are omitted. The list can be ordered in ascending or descending order by three different criteria:

1. **Relevance** (default)
2. **Publication time**
3. **Popularity measures**, e.g. retweets, number of views, likes, etc.

Paging should also be provided. Finally, several types of filter have to be provided to make the navigation in the collection of social media items easier. Namely, the following filters are supported:

1. **Social media platform:** the user keeps only items from specific platforms e.g. Twitter.
2. **Publication Date:** the user keeps only items in a specific time range.
3. **Language:** the user keeps only items written in the specified languages, e.g. en, de, etc.

Priority (5/5): Without the implementation of retrieval the user cannot see any information. To this end, we set the priority of this feature to the highest value.

Stability (4/5): This feature is well defined and it is unlikely to change dramatically in a future version of the system. However it is possible that new filters and new sorting fields will be added.

<FR-5> The user should be able to perform a search in the collection of items related to a source.

Description: Given a set of social media items related to a source, the user should be able to perform a search on these items by using the following queries:

1. **text-based query:** the user can specify a text query and retrieve only items that are relevant to it. Logical operators (AND, OR, NOT) between terms of the query are also supported.
2. **location-based query:** the user can specify a location-based query i.e. a bounding box, and retrieve only items that are relevant to it.
3. **hybrid:** a combination of the previous types of query.

The same set of filters and sort fields that are available in **<FR-4>**, are also available for querying.

Priority (4/5): This requirement does not affect the core functionality of the system, but adds an important functionality in the platform.

Stability (3/5): The way that the user searches to his/her collections may change in future versions of the tool.

<FR-6> The user should be able to get statistics for each source he/she owns.

Description: Given a source of interest, the user should be able to get a set of statistics for this source, derived from the related items. Namely, the following statistics should be supported:

1. top N social media platforms, in terms of items
2. top N accounts (pages, channels, users, etc.) in terms of published items
3. top N shared URLs
4. top N domains (from the URLs)
5. top N items based on popularity measures (#views, #shares, etc)
6. top N images
7. top N tags

Also several types of filter have to be provided. Namely, the following filters are supported:

1. **Social media platform:** the user gets top N fields only for a specified platform.
2. **Publication Date:** the user gets top N fields in a specific time range.
3. **Language:** the user gets top N fields from items written in the specified language.

Priority (3/5): This is a very important feature for the end user, in order to get insight for the source of interest. However, this requirement does not affect the rest functionalities of the system. So, the priority is set to medium.

Stability (4/5): This feature is unlikely to change.

<FR-7> The user should be able to get topics, detected in his/her collections.

Description: The user should be able to retrieve topics that are detected in his/her collections of items. A topic is a set of items that discuss the same subject. The relation between sources and topics is **many-to-many** i.e. multiple sources could discuss the same topic but a source could also contain multiple topics. Regarding the representation of a topic, the user should be able to see the following fields:

1. a set of contributors
2. a set of representative tags

3. location
4. start-end date
5. set of representative items

Priority (3/5): Detected topics are very useful for the user to get insight in the sources of interest. However, the system keeps its main functionality, either without this feature. So, its priority is considered as medium.

Stability (1/5): The way that topics are detected, extracted and presented is going to change in future versions of the system.

<FR-8> The user should be able to retrieve topics relevant to a specific query.

Description: The user should be able to search for topics, by using the following types of queries:

1. **text-based query:** the user can specify a text query and retrieve topics that are relevant to it. Logical operators (AND, OR, NOT) between terms of the query are also supported.
2. **location-based query:** the user can specify a location-based query i.e. a bounding box, and retrieve topics that are relevant to it.
3. **hybrid:** a combination of the previous types of queries.

Priority (3/5): This requirement does not affect the rest functionalities of the system. So, the priority is set to medium.

Stability (3/5): The way that search of topics takes place is expected to change in future versions of the system but not radically.

<FR-9> The user has to be authenticated in order to use the system.

Description: To avoid abuse of the system, every user needs to first be authenticated.

Priority (5/5): Without this feature no user can use the system, and thus we set this to the highest value.

Stability (5/5): This is unlikely to change in a future version of the system.

#	Functional Requirements	Priority	Stability
1	The user has to be able to insert a new source of interest into the system for monitoring	5/5	5/5
2	The user should be able to delete a source of interest, previously inserted by him/her	5/5	5/5
3	The user should be able to get a list of sources, inserted by him/her	5/5	5/5
4	The user has to be able to retrieve social media items related to a source	5/5	4/5
5	The user should be able to perform a search in the collection of items related to a source	4/5	3/5
6	The user should be able to get statistics for each source he/she owns	3/5	4/5
7	The user should be able to get topics, detected in his/her collections	3/5	1/5
8	The user should be able to retrieve topics relevant to a specific query	3/5	3/5
9	The user has to be authenticated in order to use the system	5/5	5/5

Table 3.1 Functional requirements of the social media monitoring tool.

3.2 Non Functional Requirements

The identified non-functional requirements are of the following types:

1. Operational Requirements
2. Security Requirements
3. Maintenance requirements
4. Legal requirements

The non-functional requirements (NFR) are presented below:

<NFR-1> The system has to collect relevant content and make it available to the users shortly after the insertion of a source.

Description: After a user inserts a new source of interest, the system has to start searching a collection of social media items as soon as possible.

Type: Operational

Fit criterion: The criterion will be met if the system makes content available to the user in less than 5 minutes after the insertion of the source.

<NFR-2> The system has to respect the rate limits imposed by social media platforms.

Description: The system should not make more requests per time slot than the number of requests allowed by each social media platform.

Type: Operational and Legal requirements

Fit criterion: The criterion will be met if the number of requests is kept lower than the official rate limits.

<NFR-3> The system has to make efficient use of resources during collection.

Description: As multiple users insert sources independently, these sources may have a high degree of overlap, e.g. containing the same or similar sets of keywords and accounts. In order to make efficient use of resources (network bandwidth, rate limits imposed by social media platforms, etc.), the system should **de-duplicate** the sources inserted by users.

Type: Operational

Fit criterion: The criterion will be met if the system does not make multiple requests to a social media platform for the same source e.g. keyword.

<NFR- 4> The system should adapt request rate for each source based on the activity of each source.

Description: As the rate of activity of each source, e.g. account or keyword-based source, is not the same, the system has to have a different request rate for each source. Namely, sources having high activity need to be monitored more frequently, whereas sources with low activity should be observed less frequently.

Type: Operational

Fit criterion: This criterion will be met if the number of requests performed for a source is increased if the activity is increased over time and the opposite.

<NFR-5> The system architecture should support REST connectors between communication interfaces.

Description: The components should be communicating with REST connectors using predefined resource signatures (URIs).

Type: Operational (Interfaces to other Systems/Applications)

Fit criterion: The requirement shall be met if components exchange data through URIs using standard HTTP calls.

<NFR-6> The design of the system shall ensure interoperability in data exchange by supporting JSON requests and responses.

Description: This NFR requires the components to exchange data using standardized and open formats to ensure the expandability and maintainability of the system. To this end, the system components should return JSON formatted responses.

Type: Operational (Interfaces to other Systems/Applications)

Fit criterion: The requirement shall be met if and the system responses are expressed in JSON.

<NFR- 7> The system should keep log files.

Description: The system should keep log files for any action that is performed between the system and the user, as well as actions that are triggered periodically within the system. This is of critical importance to ensure maintainability and fast bug-fixing for rolling deployments.

Type: Maintainability & Support

Fit criterion: The criterion will be met if the system logs every important transaction.

<NFR- 8> System should support multiple social media platforms.

Description: The system should support the collection of social media items from the following platforms:

1. Twitter
2. YouTube
3. Facebook
4. GooglePlus
5. Flickr

Type: Operational

Fit criterion: The criterion will be met if the system given a source can collect available items from all the above platforms.

<NFR- 9> The system should have a common data model for all the collected content (Items, MediaItems, WebPages, Users) regardless of the underlying social media platform.

Description: Each platform has its own representation for each piece of data but there are similar fields that keep similar piece of information among all platforms. To this end, the system has to define a common data model for all the objects collected from it, and expose this common representation to the users.

Type: Operational

#	Non Functional Requirement
1	The system has to collect relevant content and make it available to the users shortly after the insertion of a source
2	The system has to respect the rate limits imposed by social media platforms
3	The system has to make efficient use of resources during collection.
4	The system should adapt request rate for each source based on the activity of each source.
5	The system architecture should support REST connectors between communication interfaces.
6	The design of the system shall ensure interoperability in data exchange by supporting JSON requests and responses
7	The system should keep log files
8	System should support multiple social media platforms
9	The system should have a common data model for all the collected content (Items, MediaItems, WebPages, Users) regardless of the underlying social media platform

Table 3.2 Non Functional Requirements of the social media monitoring tool.

4 Application

4.1 User interface

The application enables users to discover how media is shared in Online Social Networks. A user can create several collections, each one linked to his/her preferences. To initiate a collection, the user must define a set of keywords, hashtags and a set of user profiles, across Social Networks, all relevant to a topic he/she wants to monitor.

Figure 4.1 User Input

Once a user has launched a collection, he/she can inspect all the gathered information in two primary sections: the Feed and the Dashboard.

The Feed presents the latest media items collected around the topic in real time. The system fetches all relevant media content, photos, videos and posts, seconds to minutes after they are published. Each item contains all the information that comes along with the post, like time, user and Social Network.

Figure 4.2 Feed view

The dashboard offers a variety of metrics and widgets that offer summary views over the collected data, enabling users to gain meaningful insights about the entity of interest. The visualizations are interactive and allow users to inspect the media that are behind these statistics.

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In more detail the dashboard consists of a number of widgets that are illustrated in the following. The first widget depicts the basic metrics (Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3 Aggregated Social Media Metrics

Each of the four indexes shown in Figure 4.3 represents a metric that expresses the popularity and diffusion of the given topic. Especially we get the total number of:

- Posts made
- Users Talking
- Users Reached
- Endorsements

Figure 4.4 Social Mix widget

Additionally these numbers can be mapped to a Social Mix graph. In this pie chart the exact amount of contribution from each individual social network is illustrated. The mix of social network sources is offered for posts, users talking, users reached and endorsements. In other words, the user can click on the four metrics of Figure 4.3 and the social mix widget changes accordingly.

Figure 4.5 Heatmap widget

The exact location (in terms of latitude, longitude) from each post is displayed in the heatmap. Zoom in/out functionalities are provided.

Figure 4.6 Users Location widget

In association with the heatmap of posts, this world map presents user location at the level of a country. Numbers can be presented as absolute values or as a percentage of total users.

The number of posts over time is depicted in a timeline visualization as illustrated in figure 4.7. The analysis can change between values per hour, day and week.

Figure 4.7 Timeline widget

The widget of figure 4.8 visualizes the top N users with most posts, the so-called influencers. N can be changed from 10 up to 200. Avatar, username and total number of posts for each user is offered along with the link to their social profile pages.

Figure 4.8 Top users widget

The top N frequent entities are represented in figure 4.9. As in the previous widget, N can be changed from 10 up to 200. Entities are divided in three categories (often, occasionally, seldom) based on the number of appearances they have and in three types (person, tag, location). Absolute values are displayed also in the table in descending order.

Figure 4.9 Top entities widget

All visualizations can be minimized or even closed in order to customize the current view based on user needs. The graphs are interactive and can be hovered to reveal more information. When data is not available, appropriate messages are shown.

Figure 4.10 Filters of UI

A number of filters are available so that both the feed and dashboard can be customized to the needs of the end user. In particular, the filters are:

- **Social Network:** Define the source of posts
- **Language:** Define the language of posts
- **Topics:** Define the topic provided from the topic detection algorithm (to be detailed in the next section), and refine the results according to the selected topic.
- **Original:** Define whether a post is shared or original
- **Type:** Define whether a post contains multimedia content or just text
- **Date:** Define a specific time window

Furthermore, in the feed view sorting criteria are available:

- **Recency:** The most recent posts according to publication time come up
- **Popularity:** The most shared posts come up
- **Relevance:** The most relevant posts comes up

As expected, one can also search for media based on specific keywords inside the collection.

An entire view of dashboard components is shown in figure 4.11.

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Figure 4.11 Example of the dashboard view

4.2 REST API

The social media monitoring tool exposes the collected data through a REST API. The API calls depicted in figure 4.12 are divided in three categories: calls related a) to the management of collections b) to the retrieval of items and c) to the retrieval of statistics per collection³.

Regarding collections management, basic CRUD operations are supported. A user identified by a unique *uid* can create a new collection (**POST** */collection*), update it (**POST** */collection/edit*), delete it (**GET** */collection/delete/{cid}*). Note that upon these actions, the specific collection is stored in MongoDB and an associated message is published on Redis in order to signal the StreamManager. To retrieve a specific collection with a unique identifier {cid} the user can call **GET** */collection/{uid}/{cid}*. As a user can create multiple collections, a method for the paged retrieval of each collections is also supported (**GET** */collection/{uid}*).

STEP social media monitoring tool

Created by manosetro@iti.gr

[Apache 2.0](#)

collections		Show/Hide	List Operations	Expand Operations
GET	<i>/collection/{uid}</i>			Returns a user's collections
GET	<i>/collection/{uid}/{cid}</i>			Returns a user's collection
GET	<i>/collection/delete/{cid}</i>			Deletes a collection
POST	<i>/collection/edit/</i>			Edits a collection
POST	<i>/collection</i>			Inserts a collection
items		Show/Hide	List Operations	Expand Operations
GET	<i>/items</i>			
GET	<i>/items/{id}</i>			Returns an item
statistics		Show/Hide	List Operations	Expand Operations
GET	<i>/{field}</i>			Top..
GET	<i>/terms</i>			Top terms
GET	<i>/heatmap/points</i>			Heatmap points
GET	<i>/timeline</i>			Timeline
GET	<i>/statistics</i>			Statistics
GET	<i>/topics</i>			Topics
GET	<i>/suggest</i>			Suggest

Figure 4.12 REST API methods of social media monitoring tool

The **GET** */items* method is the main method used for the retrieval of items related to a collection. The set of parameters depicted in figure 4.13 specifies the retrieved items. The most important parameter is the *collection* that defines the id of a collection⁴. Having specified a collection, a query is formulated according to the keywords and the accounts contained in the definition of the collection. This query is

³ For an extensive documentation of the provided API check <http://188.214.128.152/doc/v0.1/>.

⁴ Although retrieval of items without the definition of a specific collection is supported by the API, this functionality is not used in the integrated version of social media monitoring tool. In any case, without the specification of a collection, the retrieved items meet the constraints imposed by the other parameters.

restructured according to the rest of the parameters of the method. The final query is sent to Solr in order to retrieve relevant content. As Solr keeps only the subset of the fields of the items that need to be indexed, the actual content is retrieved from MongoDB through subsequent calls in this service.

items Show/Hide List Operations Expand Operations

GET /items

Parameters

Parameter	Value	Description	Parameter Type	Data Type
since	<input type="text"/>	Filter results since a date	query	string
until	<input type="text"/>	Filter results until a date	query	string
source	<input type="text"/>	Filter by source	query	string
language	<input type="text"/>	Filter by language	query	string
original	<input type="text"/>	Filter and return only original items	query	string
type	<input type="text"/>		query	string
sort	<input type="text"/>	Sort	query	string
q	<input type="text"/>	Query term	query	string
topicQuery	<input type="text"/>		query	string
collection	<input type="text"/>	Filter by collection ID	query	string
user	<input type="text"/>	Filter by user ID	query	string

Response Messages

HTTP Status Code	Reason	Response Model	Headers
405	Invalid input		

[Try it out!](#)

Figure 4.13 REST method for the retrieval of items

The third group contains methods that retrieve statistics and other information related to collections. This group includes a method to get top values for any field (e.g. top URLs, tags, etc.), a method to get the timeline of items for a specific collection, a method for topics and finally a method for several statistics such as the number of items and users, items per social media platform, etc. For the implementation of these functionalities the Faceting mechanism⁵ and Statistics Component⁶ of Solr are used, as described in section 5.2. For topic detection, a clustering component⁷ is used with Lingo as the chosen clustering algorithm that is claimed to create diverse clusters with high quality descriptions⁸.

⁵ <https://cwiki.apache.org/confluence/display/solr/Faceting>

⁶ <https://cwiki.apache.org/confluence/display/solr/The+Stats+Component>

⁷ <https://cwiki.apache.org/confluence/display/solr/Result+Clustering>

⁸ <http://doc.carrot2.org/#section.advanced-topics.fine-tuning.choosing-algorithm>

5 Implementation

The STEP social media monitoring tool is built on top of a set of independent services that are deployed over Docker⁹ containers. The overall architecture of the social media monitoring tool and the interconnections between the different services is depicted in figure Figure 5.1. Each of these services is a separate *Docker image*. As the tool is a multi-container Docker application, Docker Compose¹⁰ is used for its deployment. To use Docker compose, the architecture specification and the dependencies between the services of figure Figure 5.1 can be defined in the form of a YAML file. Then, Docker Compose uses this configuration file to deploy the services and create a common virtual network for the communication between them.

Figure 5.1 Social media monitoring tool architecture

More specifically the tool consists of the following modules - services:

⁹ Docker (<https://www.docker.com/>) is a software “packaging” technology that facilitates deployment and testing.

¹⁰ <https://docs.docker.com/compose/>

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- **StreamManager**¹¹ - This supports the continuous monitoring of five social media streams: Twitter, Facebook, Flickr, Google+ and YouTube to collect content relevant to a set of user-selected keywords, user accounts or locations, by using the corresponding APIs that are provided by each platform. It is described in more detail in section 5.1.
- **MongoDB**¹² - This is an open-source, document database used to store the data collected from the StreamManager, such as Items, Media Items, Web Pages, Users, etc.
- **Solr**¹³ - This is an open source enterprise search platform built on top of Apache Lucene. It is used primarily for full text indexing of the collected social media items and the retrieval of content based on free text queries.
- **Web component** – This service consists of two parts that run on the same docker container:
 - **MM API**: A REST API that provides access to the collected social media items and exposes several analytics related to them.
 - **Web UI**: The web interface of the tool described in section 5.3.
- **Redis**¹⁴ - This is an open source, in-memory data structure store, used as database, cache and message broker. It is primarily used as a publish/subscribe service to enable the different components of the tool to communicate with each other.
- **Graylog**¹⁵ – This is an open source log aggregator and management service, which aggregates and maintains the logs produced by the rest of the services.

The StreamManager is a Java-based service that collects content posted in social media platforms and subsequently, stores and indexes it in MongoDB and Solr respectively. The incoming collections that represent a topic of interest for a user of the STEP platform, are forwarded to the StreamManager through Redis. Shortly after the set up of a new collection, the StreamManager starts to poll the aforementioned social media APIs for new content. Ultimately, content associated with the collection of interest is exposed to the end user, creator of the collection, through the MM REST API. The REST API is also used by the user interface of the web application.

¹¹ <https://github.com/MKLab-ITI/mklab-stream-manager>

¹² <https://www.mongodb.com/>

¹³ <http://lucene.apache.org/solr/>

¹⁴ <http://redis.io/>

¹⁵ <https://www.graylog.org/>

Figure 5.2 Entity-Relationship data model of social media monitoring tool

The data model of the STEP social media monitoring tool is depicted in figure Figure 5.2. The basic entity of the collected data is an Item that represents the messages posted in social media platforms. Items are published by social media accounts that are represented by the User entity. Also an item may contain Media Items (in case of embedded multimedia content) or may be associated with Web Pages (in case of URLs in the text of the message). All these entities are stored and indexed in MongoDB and Solr respectively. In MongoDB's terminology, a separate Collection is used for each of these entities. In case of Solr each of these entities corresponds to a different Solr Core.

The right side of the figure depicts the entity that represents the collections created by the users of the tool. These collections, which are also kept in MongoDB, are associated with Queries/Sources (e.g. keyword-based queries, account-based queries, etc.). Queries are not stored persistently in a database, but exist only inside the StreamManager as described in the next section.

Between the left and the right part of the Entities-Relationships model there are two implicit relationships that connect Items with Collections and Queries. These relationships are not materialized, but are generated on the fly by using the Solr querying facilities. More specifically, neither the collected items nor the collections and queries keep an explicit association to each other. Instead, these relationships come up during retrieval when a user asks for the items of a specific collection. Given the collection, the related queries are generated, transformed to complex Solr queries and used for the retrieval of indexed items.

5.1 Stream manager for social media

The StreamManager monitors a set of five social media streams: Twitter, Facebook, Flickr, Google+ and YouTube to collect incoming content relevant to collections using the corresponding API that is provided by each service. The StreamManager acts as a polling consumer that performs requests to each of the social media platforms periodically to retrieve new content.

Figure 5.3 De-duplication of collections in stream manager

To meet the functional and non-functional requirements of the tool, the StreamManager de-duplicates the incoming collections to form a set of queries for each collection. A collection is defined as a set of keywords or social media accounts. When such a collection is inserted in the StreamManager, each of these keywords, accounts and locations results in a new source/query. As different users can be interested in similar topics, the created collections are expected to have considerable overlap in terms of the underlying sets of keywords and accounts. As depicted in figure Figure 5.3, the StreamManager keeps track of the number of times that a keyword or an account is included in a collection. To this end, more resources (e.g. number of requests) are allocated to the most important sources. In the same way, when a user removes a collection, the sources under monitoring are updated accordingly.

From a technical point of view, each of the supported social media platforms is monitored from a different thread inside the StreamManager. Rate limits imposed by each platform are fully respected by sharing the available requests in each of the sources under monitoring. The default request period for each source is 30 minutes but this rate is adapted according to the importance of each source. The collected items then pass through a processing pipeline that includes language detection and named entities extraction by using the Stanford NLP toolkit¹⁶. Also a set of filters is applied sequentially to discard items of low quality. Namely, items with limited text information or items that seem to be spam messages are discarded. More specifically, for the identification of potential spam items we use a set of simple heuristic rules based on the number of hashtags, URLs and mentions contained in an item. The intuition is that items with limited text information and many hashtags or mentions are items that aim to redirect the user to the embedded URLs. Also, we use a list of swear words and discard items that contain any of them. The remaining items are forwarded for storing and indexing in MongoDB and Solr respectively.

¹⁶ <http://nlp.stanford.edu/software/>

5.2 Data management: storing & indexing

For data management (storage and indexing), two technical solutions were chosen: MongoDB and Solr. As mentioned in the previous sections, MongoDB is used for persistent storage of the collected content, while Solr is used primarily for text indexing and retrieval, and secondarily for the computation of useful analytics.

For the communication of StreamManager with MongoDB and the mapping of Java objects¹⁷ to MongoDB documents and vice versa, the Morphia¹⁸ POJO framework is used. An example of a stored item in MongoDB is depicted in figure Figure 5.4. For the retrieval from MongoDB, a broad set of query operations is supported. However in our case the only way of retrieval from MongoDB is based on the `_id` field of each stored document. For example the item of figure Figure 5.4 can be retrieved by using the query `{"_id": "Twitter#763525927527706625"}`. As the `_id` is by default indexed in MongoDB, the retrieval by id is extremely fast. In a similar way media items, web pages and users are stored and retrieved in and from separate MongoDB collections.

```
{
  "id": "Twitter#763525927527706625",
  "className": "gr.iti.mklab.framework.abstractions.socialmedia.items.TwitterItem",
  "source": "Twitter",
  "title": "Bringing #Republicans to the #ClimateChange Table https://t.co/hAz1Bfwy4v #ActOnClimate #WeMeanIt https://t.co/VZzcJzVroX",
  "tags": [
    "Republicans",
    "ClimateChange",
    "ActOnClimate",
    "WeMeanIt"
  ],
  "uid": "Twitter#16593287",
  "mentions": [
  ],
  "pageUrl": "https://twitter.com/TreeBanker/statuses/763525927527706625",
  "links": [
    "http://nyti.ms/1LP9U1B"
  ],
  "publicationTime": NumberLong(1470873741000),
  "insertionTime": NumberLong(1470873848932),
  "mediaIds": [
    "Twitter#763525924776271872"
  ],
  "language": "en",
  "original": true,
  "likes": NumberLong(0),
  "shares": NumberLong(0),
  "comments": NumberLong(0)
}
```

Figure 5.4 Item example stored in MongoDB

Figure Figure 5.5 depicts an example of a collection created by a user of the platform. The title of collection is “climate change” and has been created by the user with id 1234567890. This collection contains eight keywords related to climate change. Apart from the `_id` based retrieval of collections, as in the case of items, collections are also retrieved by the owner id to support the scenario that a platform user asks for the collections he/she created. To this end, this field is also indexed.

The collected content is stored in three Solr cores: Items, MediaItems and WebPages¹⁹. As the main functionality of Solr is text-based retrieval and field-based statistics, we only index a subset of the fields of items, media items and web pages in Solr, such as the title, description, publicationTime, source, user id, latitude and longitude. Note that the selection of these fields aims at minimizing the size of Solr cores. Storing is disabled as the actual content is stored in MongoDB. As items is the main entity for the platform we describe only indexing and retrieval from this core.

¹⁷ <https://github.com/MKLab-ITI/mklab-framework-common/blob/master/src/main/java/gr/iti/mklab/framework/common/domain/Item.java>

¹⁸ <http://mongodb.github.io/morphia/>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/MKLab-ITI/mklab-framework-client/tree/master/src/main/resources/solr>

```

{
  "_id": "5919412345678901453707008551",
  "title": "climate change",
  "ownerId": "1234567890",
  "keywords": {
    "0": {
      "keyword": "climate change"
    },
    "1": {
      "keyword": "greenhouse gases"
    },
    "2": {
      "keyword": "global warming"
    },
    "3": {
      "keyword": "low-carbon"
    },
    "4": {
      "keyword": "carbon dioxide"
    },
    "5": {
      "keyword": "zero emissions"
    },
    "6": {
      "keyword": "industrial emissions"
    },
    "7": {
      "keyword": "greenhouse effect"
    }
  },
  "accounts": [
  ],
  "creationDate": NumberLong(1453707008000),
  "updateDate": NumberLong(1467720996000),
  "since": NumberLong(1453620608000),
  "status": "stopped",
  "stopDate": NumberLong(1467720996000)
}

```

Figure 5.5 Example of stored collection in MongoDB

```

"accounts": [
  {
    "username": "CreteRegion",
    "source": "Twitter",
    "id": "461959698",
    "name": "Περιφέρεια Κρήτης",
    "_id": "461959698"
  },
  {
    "username": "Περιφέρεια Κρήτης",
    "source": "Youtube",
    "id": "UCiZwWU0REgrLsG7S2m7Ebpw",
    "name": "",
    "_id": "UCiZwWU0REgrLsG7S2m7Ebpw"
  }
],

```

Figure 5.6 Example of accounts in a collection

Solr supports two types of query: queries and filter queries. The former takes part in the calculation of the score of the retrieved document, while the latter does not. Given a collection, a complex query is formulated to describe it. For example given the collection of figure Figure 5.5, the following keyword-based query is constructed:

$Q_c \rightarrow$ "climate change" OR "greenhouse gases" OR "global warming" OR "low-carbon" OR "carbon dioxide" OR "zero emissions" OR "industrial emissions" OR "greenhouse effect"

Based on the above query a basic Solr query is defined:

$(title:Q_c) OR (description:Q_c) OR (tags:Q_c)$

If the collection contains accounts and location, the above query is formulated accordingly to include them. To take into account the accounts depicted in figure Figure 5.6 we have to formulate the query accordingly to include them. In this specific example there are two accounts, one in Twitter and one in YouTube. Each of the collected items is tagged with the id of the user that published it. For example the items published by the first account in figure Figure 5.6 are tagged with `uid=Twitter#461959698`. In that way to retrieve items from these accounts in the results we add the following part in the collection query:

```
uid:(Twitter#461959698 OR Youtube#UCiZwWU0REgrLsG7S2m7Ebpw)
```

Note that the retrieved documents are scored based only on the collection query.

The generated query can be refined by additional filter queries. For example if the user is interested only in items posted on Twitter, the filter query `source:Twitter` is added. If the user asks for items in a specific time window, the filter query `publicationTime:[since TO until]` is added. As we want to support free text search within a collection, user-defined queries are also added as filter queries. For example if the user of the platform specifies a query Q_u , then `(title:Q_u) OR (description:Q_u) OR (tags:Q_u)` is added as a filter query. These filter queries do not contribute to the score of the items. The intuition behind this setting is that the score of a retrieved item corresponds to the relevance of the item to the collection. To this end, we want this score to be calculated only by the query Q_c that represents the collection, namely the query generated by the keywords, the user accounts and the locations. All the other queries solely refine the result set by keeping only the items that meet them.

For the ranking of the retrieved items different criteria can be defined. The three most common are the relevance score of the items, their publication time and finally popularity. For popularity we use the number of likes and shares that an item receives over time by computing their weighted average: $\text{popularity} = 0.3 * \text{shares} + 0.7 * \text{likes}$.

To calculate the top values for a specific field in a collection and other statistics like number of items, number of users, etc., two Solr mechanisms are used: faceted search and statistics component. For faceted search we define a query for the collection in the same way as described above. Additionally, a facet field is defined for which a GROUP BY query will be executed. For example given a collection and defining `uid` as a facet field, the faceted search will retrieve the number of items relevant to the collection, grouped by `uid`. In that way we can get the top users contributed to this collection. Other fields that can be used include URLs, tags, etc.

The Statistics component is used in a similar way to get simple statistics per field in the context of a collection. Statistics include the min/max value of the field, sum or mean value, distinct count, etc. Note that more of these operations can be defined only for numerical fields (e.g. min/max/mean/sum), while others can be defined for any field. The query that represents the collection is defined in the same way as described above. For example, if we want to calculate the distinct count of users that contribute in a collection we can define the distinct count operation. This component is very useful for the calculation of metrics like *reach*²⁰ and *endorsement* in a collection. For example, we can use the sum operation in the number of followers of the users that have posted items in the collection to estimate the reach value. In a similar way we can use the sum or the mean value of likes of the items of the collection as an estimated value of the endorsement of the collection.

For topic detection the result clustering component of Solr is used²¹. This component attempts to discover groups of related search results (items) and assign a human-readable label to these groups. For the retrieval of the results for a given collection we follow the same procedure described above. Then the clustering component is used to group these items in separate clusters that represent different aspects

²⁰ Reach is a measure of the size of the audience of a collection. In other words the potential number of users that have seen the content related to a specific collection.

²¹ <https://cwiki.apache.org/confluence/display/solr/Result+Clustering>

discussed in the collection. The quality of the clusters depends on the number of the documents (items) used for clustering. The use of more items, gives better results but increase the execution time of the procedure. To this end, we opted for the use of a fixed number of latest items in the collection. More specifically, we formulate the query representing the collection as described in this section and add a sort by parameter that combines relevance and recency (*sort=(publicationTime desc, score desc)*). We limit the number of the results to 2000 results according to the aforementioned ranking. Solr supports three different algorithms for clustering: Lingo, Suffix Tree Clustering and k-means. We opted for Lingo that stated to produce clusters of high diversity with long and descriptive labels²². The clustering component outputs a set of clusters, each of which contains a set of labels and the portion of the documents assigned to it. However, in our system we use only the labels and not the assignment of the items. As we want to retrieve per topic items, we use the labels of each cluster to formulate a Solr query used as filter query.

5.3 Visualisations

The Visualization Component is web based and uses the following technologies:

- HTML5 for structuring the basic content
- CSS3 for layout manipulation
Normalize.css²³ is used for better cross-browser consistency
- JavaScript for controlling components
Furthermore a set of JavaScript libraries are used. Namely:
 - Simpleheat²⁴ for drawing heatmaps with Canvas, used by the Heatmap Visualization (Figure 4.7)
 - JustGage²⁵ for generating gauges, used by the Users Location visualization (Figure 4.7)
- jQuery for easier document traversal
A jQuery plugin²⁶ is used for animating numbers in the Aggregated Social Media Metrics (see Figure 4.3)
- Foundation for responsive design
With Foundation Grid²⁷ visualizations adapt to various screen sizes, from desktops to mobile devices. Each screen is divided to 12 columns and based on their size to three categories:
 - Small screens.
A screen with max width set of 640px (screen size <= 640px)
 - Medium screens.
A screen with min width set of 641px and max width of 1024px (640px < screen size <= 1024px)
 - Large screens.
A screen with min width set of 1025px (screen size > 1024px)

According to screen size category, each visualization fits in a number of columns, from the 12 available.

²² <http://doc.carrot2.org/#section.advanced-topics.fine-tuning.choosing-algorithm>

²³ <https://github.com/necolas/normalize.css/>

²⁴ <https://github.com/mourner/simpleheat>

²⁵ <http://justgage.com/>

²⁶ <https://github.com/aishek/jquery-animateNumber>

²⁷ <http://foundation.zurb.com/grid.html>

Visualization	Small Screen	Medium Screen	Large Screen
Aggregated Social Media Metrics (Figure 4.3)	12/12	6/12	3/12
Social Mix (Figure 4.4)	12/12	12/12	4/12
Heatmap (Figure 4.5)	12/12	12/12	4/12
Users Location (Figure 4.6)	12/12	12/12	5/12
Timeline (Figure 4.7)	12/12	12/12	8/12
Active Users (Figure 4.8)	12/12	12/12	7/12
Entities (Figure 4.9)	12/12	12/12	12/12

- D3.js for producing graphs
All graphs are built with D3 basic models, customized to get the desired result. Especially, the Entities visualization (Figure 5.9) uses the Force Layout²⁸ component of D3.js to provide most of the functionality behind the transitions, animations and collisions. For each Entity, we define frequency, appearance (seldom, occasionally, often) and color. Also there is a variety of parameters affecting the visualization, such as:
 - Gravity
A force that can push bubbles towards the center of the layout
 - Friction
Velocity decay during re-positioning
 - Charge
If bubbles will attract (positive value) or repel (negative value) each other
 - Alpha
A parameter to scale the movement of bubbles

For the collision detection, charge parameter for each bubble is set to the negative of the radius squared, divided by 8. The bigger the bubble is, the more it repels others. Dividing by 8 scales the repulsion. Gravity is set to -0.01 and friction to 0.9 to ensure bubbles are slightly pushed away from the center of the layout, but prevent them from scattering away.

- Mapbox.js for designing maps
Heatmap has zoom in/out functionality. Once zoom level changes, points are re-calculated based on the zoom factor and bounding box of the viewable area.

All the data needed for the visualizations are retrieved from the REST API of section 4.2. By using AJAX requests a JSON file with all the necessary information is pulled and used to produce the visualizations.

5.4 User management

In this version of the tool, there is no need for user management. Any external user management service can be used to ensure that the users of the platform and the collections they create can be identified. The only component of social media monitoring tool that is aware of users is the REST API. During the creation of a collection, the information of the user that creates it is kept as a field in the collection. In that way, each user can retrieve through the API only the collections created by him/her.

²⁸ <https://github.com/d3/d3-3.x-api-reference/blob/master/Force-Layout.md>

5.5 Data logging

Data logging within the social media monitoring tool is handled by Graylog, which is deployed as a Docker component and aggregates the logs produced by the other components of the tool. The GELF²⁹ format on top of the UDP protocol is used for the communication of the services with the Graylog server.

In order to avoid the vast majority of unnecessary logs the logging level is set to WARN for all services except for the StreamManager, which uses a broad set of INFO logs to ensure that the component works properly. More specifically, we generate logs for the following actions:

- Insertion of a new collection
- Deletion of a collection
- Update of an existing collection
- Creation of new source/query
- Update of an existing source/query
- Deletion of source/query

Also the following statistics are kept during the operation of the StreamManager:

- Number of items retrieved per request period for each source
- Number of items filtered from each filter
- Number of items stored and indexed

²⁹ <http://docs.graylog.org/en/2.0/pages/gelf.html>

6 Case Study

Consider the case of a municipality planning to implement a new policy to reduce food waste in its area. Given this scenario, the municipality officers may want to find related policies and discussions about these issues in different social media platforms. Also, discussions about the causes of food waste can be a valuable source of information. The social media monitoring tool can be used for the collection of such content and can make easier the navigation of the user in the large amounts of collected content.

As a first step, the user has to create a new collection related to food waste. In figure Figure 6.1 a new collection is created, containing a set of keywords and a set of accounts that are relevant to food waste. For example keywords include “food waste”, “food loss”, “food recycling” and “food cycle”. Also as the concatenated versions of these phrases are typically used as tags in social media platforms #foodwaste, #foodloss and #fightfoodwaste were also included. Regarding accounts, four known Twitter users were used: @REFoodUK, @EUrefresh, @ThePigIdea and @LFHW_UK. As these accounts publish messages related to food waste, the collection is enriched with content that may contain different keywords except the defined ones.

Figure 6.1 Insert a new collection related to food waste

Figure 6.2 Food waste collection, one hour after its creation

Figure 6.3 Collected items related to food waste

After the creation of the collection, the tool starts to retrieve and make available related items. The status of the collection around one hour after its creation is depicted in figure Figure 6.2. At that stage

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about 5k items have already been collected. Figure Figure 6.3 presents the feed view of these items. The user can leverage the set of filters on the left side of the tool in order to find subsets of messages of interest. For example using the query “food recycling” in the search box on the left, he/she can browse in the items that are related to this aspect (figure Figure 6.4). As depicted in the figure, there are messages from twitter related to food waste sorting in Copenhagen. Also another tweet is related to a London project aiming to prevent food waste and to promote healthy eating. In a similar way, the user of the platform can discover similar items related to projects, ideas and discussions. For example in figure Figure 6.5 a similar search in Twitter items with the word city retrieves content related to food waste in different cities.

Figure 6.4 Search collection for items related to food recycling.

Figure 6.5 Search collection for items mentioning the word city.

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Figure 6.6 Top tags of the collection

Figure 6.7 Items related to zero waste week campaign

The top tags in this collection are depicted in figure Figure 6.6. The second most often tag is *#zerowasteweek*. This tag was used during a campaign in the United Kingdom to increase awareness of citizens about waste reduction, recycling etc. One of the important aspects during the campaign was the issue of food waste. Using this discovered tag the user of the platform can navigate in the items published about the campaign (figure Figure 6.7) in order to gain some insights for the planning and design of

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similar campaigns in the future. It is important to mention that these items contain URLs that point to external sites that contain potentially valuable information related to the issue of food waste. In that way the platform can be a powerful means of discovering such information sources.

7 Limitations and Future Work

This deliverable describes the initial version of the STEP social media monitoring tool. It presents the features that were integrated during the first cycle of the module implementation.

As it was decided in the consortium, and also since the informed feedback from the end users came at a later stage after the start of the project, the first implementation of the social media monitoring tool was largely based on the pre-existing version that had been developed by CERTH before the start of the project, and was adapted to be integrated with the first version of the STEP platform, with the aim to be initially evaluated by keen citizens and the authorities.

A second set of user requirements is expected to stem from this evaluation process that will drive the second round of specifications and development.

A number of new features that have already emerged as important after the first hands-on sessions with the pilots include:

- a) New algorithmic and analysis approaches for sorting content items based on ratings and similarity, social media accounts recommendations, improved topic detection and topic-based retrieval. More specifically:
 - i. Sort content according to ratings using similarity measures (suggested by pilots). An algorithm that takes into account both the user's rating about a specific content item, as well as its similarity with other content items will be used for re-ranking the content, thus presenting the user with a list adapted to his/her personal interests.
 - ii. Embed automated translation for content items (suggested by pilot partners). The automatic translation component will be also embedded in the social media monitoring tool.
 - iii. Suggest social media accounts to include in search, based on entered keywords. An account recommendation algorithm will be implemented so as to automatically suggest the inclusion of other social media accounts in the collection when a user enters a topic of interest.
 - iv. Improve topic detection. Improved algorithms for topic detection will be used, especially focusing on better support of the languages of the pilot sites.
 - v. Improve topic-based retrieval. Enhanced algorithms will be used for topic-based retrieval with the goal to increase the precision and recall of the retrieved content.
- b) Improved query formation through geo-located search and keyword filtering at query time. More specifically:
 - i. Restrict search to specific locations (suggested by pilot partners). Each pilot site administration will be able to filter-out the results from the collections, by keeping only the content-items that emerged from their specific territory of interest.
 - ii. Exclude keywords when creating a collection (suggested by pilots). Users will be able to enter keywords that they want to be excluded from their query when creating a new collection.
 - iii. Search for individual keywords in different social media (suggested by pilots). Users will be able to define in which social media they want to search for each keyword.
 - iv. Online help for the query creation dialogues (suggested by pilots). Online help will be provided also at query creation time, and not only when viewing results as is currently the case.

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- c) Pilot site-based user and content management, i.e. each pilot will be able to manage their own content collections, which will not be available to authorities from other pilot sites.
- d) Advanced content analytics allowing content item rating, new filters and extended monitoring of selected items. More specifically:
 - i. Remove and rate significance of content (suggested by pilot partners). Authorities will be able to rate the significance of each content item retrieved, or even delete it from the collection.
 - ii. Filter by excluding keywords (suggested by pilot partners). A user may filter out content from the collections using specific keywords he/she does not wish to see within the content.
 - iii. Extended monitoring of selected items (suggested by pilot partners). For specific content items that the user will select, the system will perform further relevant content collection, by gathering discussions and follow-ups for it (e.g. tweet replies, Facebook comments, etc.).
- e) More animations and visualizations in the dashboard and in the citizens view, including temporal animation of the emerging topics that are discovered by the topic detection algorithm.
- f) Feeding e-participation conversations through automated discovery of relevant social media content. Finally, for the citizens' view, an enhanced scenario of usage is foreseen. In this respect, the conversations that a user is participating to in terms of the e-participation module will be enriched with relevant content items from social media that will be automatically discovered by the social media monitoring tool. To achieve that, the current discussions in the e-participation will feed the tool, which will then automatically extract relevant topics of interest. Subsequently social media monitoring will be performed based on those topics and the results will be returned to the citizens as suggested content items to be used in the conversations he/she participated in the STEP platform.

The above enhancements will be gradually implemented in the forthcoming period with the aim to be evaluated in terms of the project campaigns. Along with any new features that will possibly emerge from the feedback that will be acquired from the campaigns, this new feature set will drive the development of the final version of the tool.

8 Appendices

The application is integrated in STEP platform. Through e-participation module user can see posts relevant to a point of interest.

The screenshot displays the 'NEW AUTO-SCANNED POSTS' section of the STEP platform. The interface features a top navigation bar with two tabs: 'ALL POSTS' (indicated by a pink circle with the number 2) and 'NEW AUTO-SCANNED POSTS' (indicated by a pink circle with the number 47). The 'NEW AUTO-SCANNED POSTS' tab is active, showing a grid of social media posts. Each post is from the user 'Crowley Green' and is timestamped '7 ώρες πριν'. The posts include various content: text, images, and video thumbnails. Below each post, there are interaction icons (likes, comments, shares) and two buttons: a green 'Use' button and a red 'Διαγραφή' (Delete) button. The posts contain the following text:

- RT @BoingBoing: Astronomy: This amazing video demonstrates levels of light pollution. [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#) [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#)
- RT @totravelplaces: Fortress of Methoni, Greece [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#) [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#)
- RT @TravelVSCO: Santorini, Greece [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#) [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#)
- Nothing like a beautiful branding identity for a beautiful island in #Greece [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#) #Sifnos #Island #Greece AMAZING!!! [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#)
- RT @worldpixstories: Greece looks so relaxing and beautiful [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#) [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#)
- enjoy the pollution @BTS_twt :C [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#)
- @richaanirudh Very good...this is the time to push and push hard to PREVENT pollution due to celebrations, at all costs and save humanity! [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#)
- RT @atrojanfootball: Come out and support Greece Athena football tomorrow night, 8:00 vs Wilson at rhino stadium, be there! [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#)
- RT @RealTillMetYou: The King and Queen for Mega's Greece cover. #TIMYThirdWheel - Cloud [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#)
- Judge approves \$86 million settlement for Californians in
- Gostei de um video @YouTube [Πάτησε για να δεις τον σύνδεσμο.](#) vs Greece 1-2 All Goals and Highlights

Figure 8.1 Auto-scanned posts in step platform